

ANALYSIS OF THE OBJECTIVE ASPECT OF CRIMES IN THE CUSTOMS SPHERE

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Abstract: This article provides a thorough analysis of the objective aspect of crimes in the customs sphere. It concludes that, based on their objective characteristics, customs-related crimes can be divided into two categories. The first category includes acts related to the illegal transfer of criminal objects across the customs border using various methods. This encompasses all customs-related crimes except for the evasion of customs fees, and their objective aspects are examined in detail. Specifically, crimes in this group involve crossing the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan in different forms: a) bypassing customs control; b) hiding from customs control; c) fraudulently using documents made to resemble customs documents or instruments; d) without declaration; and e) using a declaration written in a different name. The second category includes acts related to the evasion of customs fees. These involve intentionally concealing and understating objects subject to customs fees, as well as deliberately evading the payment of customs fees established by the state. Crimes in this category are objectively committed through intentionally hiding objects subject to customs fees, intentionally understating the value of objects subject to customs fees, and other deliberate methods of evading customs fees. The article analyzes current criminal legal norms, other legal documents, scholarly opinions, and the provisions of the decisions of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the objective side of customs-related crimes. The author's conclusions are presented based on each case analyzed.

Keywords: crimes in the customs sphere, the objective aspect of crimes, evasion of customs control, concealment from customs control, customs documents, customs instruments, declaration, customs fees, concealing or understating objects subject to customs fees, evasion of payment of customs fees.

The objective side of a crime involves the process of socially dangerous and illegal encroachment on legally protected interests. This process is viewed as a sequence of events that begins with the criminal action (or inaction) of the subject and concludes with the occurrence of a criminal result.

The objective aspect of customs crimes serves as the primary feature that unifies these crimes into a single group. All these crimes are connected to the transportation of objects across the customs border. This category of crimes includes the transfer of objects across the customs border by various means, such as international mail, pipeline transport, and electricity transmission networks, involving the export from or import into the Republic of Uzbekistan. Typically, customs-related crimes are committed through active actions, although there are instances of criminal inaction. In such cases, crimes are committed by multiple partners, including organized groups, where the role of some partners may not involve the direct transfer of goods across the customs border.

Based on the objective aspect, customs-related crimes can be divided into two categories:

1. Actions related to the illegal transfer of criminal objects across the customs border using various methods. This category encompasses all customs-related crimes except for the evasion of customs duties.
2. Deliberate concealment and understatement of objects subject to customs duties, as well as acts related to the evasion of customs duties, which include intentional evasion of customs duties established by the state.

Crimes in the first category, as outlined in articles 130, 130-1, 182, 244-3, 244-4, 246, and 250-1 of the Criminal Code, are objectively committed in various forms at the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- Avoiding customs control.
- Hiding from customs control.
- Fraudulently using documents resembling customs documents or instruments.
- Without declaration.
- Using an aliased declaration.

The illegal transfer of objects across the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan by bypassing customs control means transferring them from a location without a customs authority or outside the designated time for customs clearance and control.

According to Article 15 of the Customs Code, the transportation of goods and/or means of transport across the customs border involves bringing goods and/or means of transport into or out of the customs territory. Actions aimed at directly transporting objects across the customs border include:

- Entry of an individual into the customs control zone.

- Entry of a vehicle into the state border crossing point of the Republic of Uzbekistan to cross the customs border.
- Delivery of goods to transport organizations or postal operators and providers of international mail and courier shipments for shipment to or from the customs territory.
- Actions of an individual aimed at crossing the customs border with goods and/or vehicles from unauthorized locations.

According to Kabulov, R., the concealment of goods from control involves transporting valuables across the customs border in specially prepared items, hidden compartments, luggage, clothes, or containers adapted for this purpose. This can manifest in various ways, such as using a suitcase or can with a double bottom, creating gaps in clothes for hiding things, and other similar methods [1, p. 232-233].

It should be recognized that customs control encompasses a set of activities carried out by customs authorities to ensure compliance with legal documents and international agreements. Bypassing customs control involves transferring the subject of the crime without inspection of the necessary documents by customs officials, from a location not designated by customs authorities, or at a time other than the specified customs control period. Concealment from customs control refers to transferring the object of the crime from secret locations or using methods that make it difficult to detect, such as altering its appearance.

Secret storage places include containers and other objects with structural capacities that are pre-processed, assembled, and equipped to vehicles for the illegal transportation of objects across the customs border. Fraudulent use of documents involves submitting forged documents, documents obtained illegally, or documents containing false information to customs control to facilitate the movement of goods and other valuables across the customs border. According to Kabulov, R., fraudulent use means that the perpetrator illegally transports goods or other assets across the customs border by presenting forged documents [1, p. 233]. This can include altering genuine documents with corrections and additions regarding the amount, volume, price of the cargo, etc.

Customs identification means include sealing, digital, letter, and other marks, placing identification marks, stamping, taking samples and copies, labeling goods, making drawings, describing scale, and sending goods with accompanying documents. Failure to include items in the declaration or including them under a different name refers to actions violating the declaration

procedure, such as submitting false information in the declaration about the type and number of items being imported or exported. According to Kabulov, R., presenting goods or other assets not declared or declared under a different name means transporting goods across the customs border under a different name or disguised as something else [1, p. 233].

According to the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, verifying the customs declaration, examining goods, and correcting errors in the customs declaration before inaccuracies are found excludes administrative or criminal liability. However, the declarant's failure to inspect and measure goods under customs control, take samples, and issue necessary documents does not exclude their responsibility [2].

The crime is considered completed once goods or other objects are transferred across the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan, either brought into its customs territory or taken out to another country, free customs region, or free warehouse. Crimes in the customs sphere may also include stages of preparation and attempts to commit the crime. Preparations include actions such as illegally obtaining licenses for the export of strategically important goods, equipping hiding places, and involving others in the crime. However, criminal cases are rarely initiated at this stage due to the secretive nature of preparatory actions and the difficulty of proving them.

In jurisprudence, a crime in the customs field is recognized as a completed crime from the moment goods cross the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This perspective allows us to consider crimes in the customs field as completed from the moment the object of the crime is transferred into the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (import) or taken out of it (export). Until such a transfer is complete, the act, regardless of the point at which the established crime ceases, will only exhibit elements of preparation for or an attempt to commit the crime.

The second category of customs crimes, namely the evasion of customs duties, is objectively committed through the following actions:

- Intentional concealment of objects subject to payment of customs duties.
- Deliberate understatement of objects for which customs fees are due.
- Deliberate evasion of customs duties by other means.

Intentional concealment of objects subject to customs duties involves deliberately failing to indicate the actual information regarding the objects subject to customs duties in the relevant documents submitted to customs authorities, as well as concealing information about their existence.

Deliberate understatement of objects subject to customs duties involves knowingly including false information about the objects in the documents submitted to customs authorities to reduce the payable amount.

It should be noted that deliberate concealment and understatement of objects subject to customs duties are methods of evading customs duties. In other words, customs duty evasion is a broader concept that includes various methods of deceiving customs authorities to reduce the amount payable to the state or local budget.

Deliberate evasion of customs duties by other means involves deliberately altering the actual state of objects, using various methods to knowingly provide false information to customs authorities, and misleading about certain facts, situations, or events to reduce the payable customs duties.

According to customs legislation, the crime is considered complete from the moment customs fees are not paid within the specified period.

From the above analysis, it can be concluded that the place, method, time, and instrument of the crime, which are optional signs of the objective aspect of the crime in the customs field, should be recognized as necessary signs for the qualification of the crime.

For instance, the objective aspect of a crime in the customs field includes the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a crucial sign of the crime. The term "customs border" refers to the borders of the customs territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the boundaries of free customs zones and free warehouses. The territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including land, territorial and internal waters, and the air space above them, constitutes the customs territory.

It should be noted that the crime involves avoiding or hiding from customs control at the customs border (where the crime is committed) or transporting the contraband object through other methods mentioned above. Transporting these items in locations not designated as the customs border is not qualified as a crime in the customs sphere.

Free customs zones and free warehouses may exist within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These areas are considered outside the customs territory of Uzbekistan unless otherwise provided by legislation. Thus, the place of the crime is a necessary sign of the objective aspect when determining the criminal actions of a person.

According to the rule that committing a crime under conditions of a general disaster, during a state of emergency, or amidst mass disturbances should be

considered aggravating circumstances, the circumstances of the crime are not necessary for determining responsibility in the customs field but should be considered aggravating when imposing a punishment [3, p. 15].

Additionally, the instrument of the crime is a necessary criterion for qualifying the crime. To be considered as having committed a crime in the customs field, it is essential that a person fraudulently uses documents and tools made to resemble customs documents or tools or uses a declaration written in another name without proper declaration.

Among the documents that legally permit the transport of certain goods and items across the customs border, a customs declaration filled out in the prescribed manner is crucial. Additionally, documents issued by organizations and institutions authorizing the transportation of specific goods, such as a reference issued by a bank for buying and transporting foreign currency, are also included. Fraudulent use of such documents involves the falsification of authentic forms by entering false information, erasing, or correcting them, as well as including descriptions and information related to other goods and items in expired documents.

Moreover, the method of committing the crime is essential in determining criminal responsibility. This includes:

- Avoiding customs control.
- Hiding from customs control.
- Using documents and tools made to resemble customs documents or tools by deception.
- Transporting the object of the crime across the border without a declaration.
- Using a declaration written in a different name.

These methods are key to understanding the nature and execution of customs-related crimes.

In conclusion, the analysis of the objective aspect of crimes in the customs sphere reveals a complex interplay of actions, documentation, and intent aimed at circumventing legal regulations. Crimes in this field can be broadly categorized into illegal transfer of goods across customs borders and evasion of customs duties, each with distinct methods and implications.

Illegal transfers involve methods such as bypassing customs control, concealing goods, and using fraudulent documents. These actions are characterized by their direct attempt to move goods across borders without proper authorization, often employing sophisticated means to avoid detection. The completion of such

crimes is marked by the actual crossing of goods into or out of the customs territory.

On the other hand, evasion of customs duties focuses on the deliberate misrepresentation or omission of information to reduce payable fees. This includes concealing objects subject to duties, understating their value, and providing false documentation. The crime is considered complete upon the failure to pay the required fees within the designated timeframe.

The place, method, and instruments of these crimes play a crucial role in their classification and the determination of criminal responsibility. The customs border of Uzbekistan serves as a pivotal element in defining the locus of the crime, while the specific techniques used to evade detection or mislead authorities highlight the premeditated nature of these offenses.

Ultimately, understanding the objective aspect of customs crimes aids in developing more effective enforcement strategies and legal frameworks to combat these offenses. It underscores the need for stringent customs control measures, accurate documentation processes, and heightened vigilance against fraudulent practices. By addressing the root causes and methods of these crimes, Uzbekistan can strengthen its customs integrity and safeguard its economic interests.

References:

1. Comments on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Z.Kh. Gulomov,
2. R.A. Zufarov, R.K. Kabulov, M.M. Kadirov, et al. – Tashkent: Adolat, 1997. – p. 233.
3. Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 20, 2023 No. 2 “On judicial practice in cases related to violation of customs legislation and smuggling”. <http://www.lex.uz/ru/docs/6404212>
4. Zakirova O.G. Criminal Liability for smuggling: Study Guide. Editor-in-chief: Prof.
5. M.H. Rustamboev. – Tashkent: TSIL, 2007. – p. 15.
6. Pasat O.A. Analiza juridico-vamală a contravențiilor, infracțiunilor vamale prevăzute de Codul vamal al României aflat în vigoare, Revista Națională de Drept”, no. 2, 2014. – p. 68.
7. Rustambaev M.H. Comments on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Special Part 2. – Tashkent: Legal Literature Publishing, 2021. – p. 535.